

DESIGN OF A STRUCTURED AND CENTRALIZED NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE FOR BARANGAY CACUTUD HALL

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ABSTRACT

This study entitled “Design of a Structured and Centralized Network Infrastructure for Cacutud Barangay Hall” aimed to develop a reliable, secure, and organized network infrastructure to address the existing networking issues within the barangay hall. The current network setup experiences weak wireless signal coverage, slow internet connectivity, lack of network segmentation, poor cable management, and the absence of a dedicated Guest WiFi network, which affect communication and operational efficiency. The study utilized a descriptive research design and adopted the PPDIOO (Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize) framework developed by Cisco Systems as the basis for the network planning and design process. Based on the findings, the researchers proposed a structured and centralized network infrastructure using Local Area Network (LAN), Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), and Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) technologies. The proposed design includes VLAN segmentation, structured cabling, centralized switching, installation of additional access points, Guest WiFi implementation, CIDR-based IP addressing and subnetting, FTP server implementation for centralized file management, and network security measures such as Access Control Lists (ACLs). The proposed network was simulated and tested using Cisco Packet Tracer and evaluated by IT experts based on ISO/IEC 27033 network security principles. Results showed that the proposed design is feasible, organized, scalable, and capable of improving connectivity, security, traffic management, IP address utilization, centralized file sharing, and operational efficiency within Barangay Cacutud Hall.

Keywords: Structured network infrastructure; centralized network design; VLAN segmentation; CIDR subnetting; FTP server; network security; Cisco Packet Tracer; PPDIOO framework.

INTRODUCTION

Reliable network infrastructure has become an essential component of modern organizations, enabling efficient communication, data sharing, security, and access to digital services. In government offices, particularly at the barangay level, network connectivity

supports administrative operations, record management, online transactions, and communication among personnel and constituents. However, poorly designed network infrastructures often result in weak connectivity, limited scalability, security vulnerabilities, and inefficient resource utilization (Cisco Systems, Inc., 2023)

Digital connectivity plays a significant role in improving governance, transparency, and public service delivery. Stable internet connectivity enables government institutions to provide services more efficiently and enhances citizen engagement through digital platforms (World Bank, 2026). Similarly, reliable network access contributes to community development by improving access to information, communication, and government services (International Telecommunication Union [ITU], 2021).

Studies have shown that structured network designs improve network performance, scalability, and manageability. Organized network architectures reduce congestion and enhance communication efficiency through proper device placement and network planning (Paguigan et al., 2022). Furthermore, centralized network management enables administrators to monitor, configure, and troubleshoot network resources more effectively from a single point of control, resulting in improved operational efficiency and network reliability (Rai et al., 2024).

Barangay Cacutud Hall currently relies on a basic network setup consisting primarily of a single router for internet connectivity. Based on the assessment conducted by the researchers, several issues were identified, including weak wireless coverage in certain offices, lack of network segmentation, absence of a dedicated guest network, limited network security measures, and disorganized cabling infrastructure. These challenges affect communication efficiency, data security, and the overall quality of public service delivery.

To address these concerns, this study proposes the design of a structured and centralized network infrastructure utilizing an Extended Star Topology, VLAN segmentation, centralized

switching, structured cabling, and strategic access point deployment. The proposed design aims to improve network coverage, enhance security, increase scalability, and support the operational requirements of Barangay Cacutud Hall.

Figure 1
Conceptual Framework

Note. The conceptual framework illustrates the development process of the proposed structured and centralized network infrastructure for Barangay Cacutud Hall. The framework follows a systematic approach beginning from data gathering up to documentation of the proposed design.

METHODS

The study followed a systematic process in developing the proposed structured and centralized network infrastructure for Barangay Cacutud Hall. The process began with data collection, which included gathering related literature and studies, conducting interviews with two barangay staff members, and identifying the necessary hardware components such as routers, switches, access points, and CCTV devices. These inputs served as the foundation

for understanding the current network environment and determining the requirements of the proposed system.

After data collection, the researchers conducted a requirements analysis to assess the existing network condition. This phase involved identifying issues such as weak wireless signal coverage, lack of network segmentation, and the absence of a Guest WiFi network. Based on the identified problems, the necessary network requirements were determined to address the limitations of the current setup.

The next stage involved the design of the proposed network infrastructure. The researchers developed a structured network topology that incorporated VLAN segmentation for different departments, an organized IP addressing scheme, and proper allocation of network devices throughout the barangay hall. The design aimed to improve connectivity, security, and overall network management.

The proposed design was then implemented through simulation using Cisco Packet Tracer. During this phase, VLANs were configured, access point placement was planned, and network security measures were established. The simulated network underwent testing and evaluation to verify connectivity, performance, and security. The evaluation ensured that VLANs functioned independently, network resources were properly segmented, and connectivity issues identified during the assessment were addressed.

Following successful testing and validation, the proposed network design was prepared for deployment. This included planning the physical placement of networking devices and organizing the infrastructure required for implementation within Barangay Cacutud Hall.

Finally, all outputs, including network diagrams, configurations, testing results, and analysis findings, were compiled and documented. The documentation serves as a reference for future implementation, maintenance, monitoring, and improvement of the proposed network infrastructure.

Table 1

Interpretation of Weighted Means Scores

Weighted Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
2.51 – 3.25	Agree
1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

RESULTS

The assessment of the existing network infrastructure of Barangay Cacutud Hall identified several issues affecting network performance, connectivity, and security. The current network setup relies on a single wireless router connected to a Converge Fiber internet service. While it provides basic internet access, weak wireless coverage was observed in areas farther from the router, particularly in the VAWC Office. The assessment also revealed the absence of network segmentation, managed switches, structured cabling, centralized management, and a dedicated Guest WiFi network.

To address these issues, a structured and centralized network infrastructure was designed. The proposed network utilizes an Extended Star Topology with a centralized switching architecture. A Cisco 2911 Router serves as the main gateway, while managed switches distribute connectivity to desktop computers, printers, CCTV cameras, servers, and wireless access points throughout the barangay hall.

The proposed design implements VLAN segmentation to separate administrative devices, CCTV systems, guest users, printers, and servers into distinct network segments. A structured IP addressing scheme was also developed using CIDR-based subnetting to improve network organization and traffic management. Additional wireless access points were strategically placed to improve signal coverage in areas with weak connectivity.

The proposed infrastructure includes security measures such as Access Control Lists (ACLs), VLAN isolation, WPA2/WPA3 wireless encryption, structured cabling, centralized CCTV integration, and a network cabinet for device organization and management. The estimated implementation cost of the proposed infrastructure is ₱149,516.

The proposed network design was evaluated by IT experts using an ISO/IEC 27033-based evaluation tool. The evaluation obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.15, interpreted as “Agree,” indicating that the proposed network infrastructure is acceptable and suitable for implementation. Among all evaluation categories, Security Architecture and Access Control received the highest weighted mean of 3.60, interpreted as “Strongly Agree.”

Table 2

Overall IT Expert Evaluation Tool result

Category	Items	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Secure Network Architecture and Design	7	3.14	Agree

2. Security Architecture and Access Control	5	3.60	Strongly Agree
3. Compliance and Standards Alignment	5	3.13	Agree
4. Risk Management	7	3.14	Agree
5. Implementation Feasibility	5	3.13	Agree
6. Resource and Cost Planning	6	3.28	Strongly Agree
7. Technology and Compatibility	5	3.20	Agree
8. Operational Planning	5	3.00	Agree
9. Performance and Capacity Planning	6	3.00	Agree
10. Documentation Quality	4	3.00	Agree
11. Network Management and Review Readiness	4	3.00	Agree
12. Overall Technical Evaluation	4	3.17	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	63	3.15	Agree

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that the existing network infrastructure of Barangay Cacutud Hall is insufficient to support the growing networking requirements of the organization. The reliance on a single router, lack of segmentation, and absence of centralized management contribute to connectivity issues, inefficient traffic distribution, and security vulnerabilities. These limitations can negatively affect communication, administrative operations, and public service delivery.

The proposed structured and centralized network infrastructure addresses these challenges through the implementation of an Extended Star Topology and centralized switching architecture. By distributing network traffic through managed switches instead of relying solely on a wireless router, the design improves network

reliability, scalability, and overall performance. The inclusion of additional wireless access points also addresses weak signal areas and enhances wireless connectivity throughout the facility.

The implementation of VLAN segmentation plays a significant role in improving network security and organization. Separating administrative devices, CCTV systems, guest users, printers, and servers into different VLANs reduces unnecessary broadcast traffic and minimizes the risk of unauthorized access. The use of Access Control Lists further strengthens security by controlling communication between network segments and protecting sensitive barangay information.

The positive evaluation results from IT experts suggest that the proposed network design is technically feasible and aligned with accepted networking standards and security principles. The high rating received in Security Architecture and Access Control demonstrates that the proposed segmentation and access control mechanisms effectively address the security concerns identified during the assessment.

Overall, the proposed network infrastructure provides a practical solution for improving connectivity, security, resource management, and operational efficiency within Barangay Cacutud Hall. The design establishes a scalable foundation that can accommodate future expansion while supporting the daily networking needs of the barangay and improving the delivery of public services.

Physical Topology

The proposed floor-based layout presents the physical placement of network devices and equipment to support organized connectivity and efficient network operations within Barangay Cacutud Hall.

Figure 2
Proposed Physical Topology / Floor-Based Layout

Logical Topology

The proposed logical topology of Barangay Cacutud Hall using an Extended Star Topology. The network consists of a Cisco 2911

Router connected to centralized switches that distribute connectivity to desktop computers, printers, servers, CCTV cameras, and wireless access points. VLAN segmentation and CIDR-based subnetting are implemented to improve network organization, security, and traffic management. The proposed topology supports reliable wired and wireless communication while providing a scalable and manageable network infrastructure for the barangay hall.

Figure 3
Logical Topology

CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that the proposed structured and centralized network infrastructure is a feasible and effective solution for addressing the networking challenges of Barangay Cacutud Hall. The assessment of the existing network revealed issues related to weak wireless coverage, lack of network segmentation, limited security measures, and inefficient network management. To address these concerns, the proposed design incorporated an Extended Star Topology, VLAN segmentation, structured IP addressing, CIDR-based subnetting, centralized switching, and improved wireless connectivity.

The evaluation results showed that the proposed network infrastructure is technically acceptable, secure, and suitable for the operational requirements of the barangay hall. The implementation of VLANs, Guest WiFi separation, and Access Control Lists (ACLs) enhances network security and traffic management, while the centralized design improves connectivity, scalability, and ease of maintenance. Overall, the proposed network infrastructure provides a reliable foundation for efficient communication, secure

data access, and improved public service delivery within Barangay Cacutud Hall.

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